

ISSN: 2181-1040
DOI: 10.26739/2181-1040
tadqiqot.uz/renaissance

JCAR

**JOURNAL OF CENTRAL
ASIAN RENAISSANCE**

**VOLUME 5 |
ISSUE 1**

2024

МАРКАЗИЙ ОСИЁ РЕНЕССАНСИ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖИЛД 5, СОН 1

ЖУРНАЛ РЕНЕССАНСА ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ
ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 1

JOURNAL OF CENTRAL ASIAN RENAISSANCE
VOLUME 5, ISSUE 1

МАРКАЗИЙ ОСИЁ РЕНЕСАНСИ ЖУРНАЛИ

№1 (2024) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-1040-2024-1>

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ЖУРНАЛ РЕНЕССАНСА ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ
JOURNAL OF CENTRAL ASIAN RENAISSANCE

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**SYSTEMATIC PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS OF THE MECHANISM OF THE
"BELT AND ROAD" PROPOSED BY CHINA**

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12170599>

ABSTRACT

In this article, the trends that influenced the development of mankind in the era of globalization were studied on a historical conceptual basis and the currently existing constructions of models were given a philosophical comparative analysis. Taking into account the dynamically developing factors of the globalization process, this article seriously investigated the modernization mechanism proposed by China "One Belt and one road", which aims to create a common future for humanity. Also in the article, the initiative "Belt and Road" and the concept of a community in which the future of humanity is common were studied on a philosophical comparative basis with the alternatives available in international experience, with a special emphasis on revealing the uniqueness of this model of modernization.

Keywords: The "Belt and Road", the future of humanity in common, international integration, modernization, polarization, mechanization, construction.

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**ХИТОЙ ТОМОНИДАН ТАКЛИФ ҚИЛИНГАН "БИР КАМАР, БИР ЙЎЛ"
МЕХАНИЗМИНИНГ ТИЗИМЛИ ФАЛСАФИЙ ТАҲЛИЛИ**

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақолада глобаллашув даврида инсоният тараққиётига таъсир кўрсатган тенденциялар тарихий концептуал асосда ўрганилди ва ҳозирги вақтда мавжуд модернизация конструкциялари фалсафий қиёсий таҳлил қилинди. Глобализация жараёнининг жадаллик билан ривожланиш омиллари ҳисобга олиниб, бу мақолада инсониятнинг умумий келажагини яратишни мақсад қилган, Хитой таклиф этаётган "Бир камар, бир йўл" модернизация механизми жиддий тадқиқ этилди. Шунингдек, мақолада "бир камар, бир йўл" ташаббуси ва инсоният келажаги умумий бўлган жамият концептсияси фалсафий қиёсий асосда халқаро тажрибада мавжуд бўлган альтернативлар билан ўрганилиб, ушбу модернизация моделининг ўзига хослигини очиб беришга алоҳида эътибор қаратилди.

Калит сўзлар: "Бир камар, бир йўл", инсониятнинг умумий бўлган келажаги, халқаро интеграция, модернизация, поляризация, механизм, конструкция.

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СИСТЕМАТИЧЕСКИЙ ФИЛОСОФСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ПРЕДЛАГАЕМОГО КИТАЕМ МЕХАНИЗМА «ПОЯСА И ПУТИ»

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье на исторической концептуальной основе были изучены тенденции, повлиявшие на развитие человечества в эпоху глобализации, а существующим в настоящее время конструкциям моделей был дан философский сравнительный анализ. Принимая во внимание динамично развивающиеся факторы процесса глобализации, в данной статье серьезно исследован предложенный Китаем механизм модернизации “Один пояс и один путь”, который направлен на создание общего будущего для человечества. Также в статье инициатива “Пояс и путь” и концепция сообщества, в котором будущее человечества является общим, были изучены на философской сравнительной основе с альтернативами, доступными в международном опыте, с особым акцентом на раскрытие уникальности этой модели модернизации.

Ключевые слова: “Один пояс и один путь”, общее будущее человечества, международная интеграция, модернизация, поляризация, механизация, строительство.

INTRODUCTION. Today’s world has entered a period of turbulence and change, with the accelerated escalation of competition among major big country, persistent geopolitical tensions, sluggish growth in the world economy, the emergence of cold-war thinking, confrontation between camps and zero-sum thinking, the rise of unilateralism, trade protectionism and hegemony, the apparent rise of populism, the worsening of the polarization between the rich and the poor, the emergence of hotspot issues in the region, and the proliferation of terrorism, cybersecurity, and major infectious diseases, Non-traditional security threats such as terrorism, cybersecurity, major infectious diseases and climate change continue to spread. The competition brought about by the new round of scientific and technological revolution and industrial change has never been fiercer; the deficits in peace, development, security and governance continue to worsen; there has been a significant increase in foreseeable and unforeseeable risks around the globe; and the synchronization of traditional and non-traditional security issues has brought to the forefront a number of issues that are seriously interfering with the overall trend of world peace and development; humankind is facing unprecedented challenges; and the future of all peoples in the world have never been so closely intertwined as they are today. Individual countries have generalized the concept of “national security” and practiced “out of joint and disconnected” in the name of “de-risking”, undermining the international economic and trade order and market rules, jeopardizing the international industrial chain supply chain, and jeopardizing the security and stability of the international humanities and human rights industries. It undermines the international economic and trade order and market rules, jeopardizes the security and stability of the international industrial chain and supply chain, blocks international humanistic, scientific and technological exchanges and cooperation, and creates obstacles to the long-term development of mankind. In an uncertain and unstable world, there is an urgent need for all countries to bridge differences through dialogue, oppose division through unity, and promote development through cooperation, and the significance of building the “Belt and Road” together is becoming more and more obvious and the prospects more promising.

In the long run, the trend of world multipolarity remains unchanged, the general direction of economic globalization remains unchanged, peace and development are still the main themes of the times, cooperation and win-win cooperation are the new requirements for conforming to the trend of the times, the aspirations of the peoples of all countries to pursue a better life and achieve common prosperity have become stronger, and the momentum of the rise of the majority of developing countries as a whole has become more and more obvious, making the responsibility of China, as the largest developing country, particularly arduous. Driven by economic globalization and the

information technology revolution, a new round of scientific and technological and industrial revolutions is being nurtured, new kinetic energy for innovation-driven development continues to accumulate, the interests of all countries are deeply integrated, and the ties among countries have never been as close as they are today. This background determines that no matter what kind of global challenges a country faces, it needs to find solutions on a global scale, and “close the door to build construction” is at the end of one's tether. The "Belt and Road" initiative conforms to the overall trend of the development of the world today, reflects the transformation of human history, and represents a national development idea that is different from unilateralism, protectionism, and extremism. It is a new idea to pursue the common development of global development in an open world economic system.

Although the joint construction of the “Belt and Road” faces some difficulties and challenges, as long as countries can start from their own long-term interests, start from the overall interests of human beings, jointly control risks, respond to challenges, promote cooperation, and the future of building the "Belt and Road" is full of hope.

LITERATURE REVIEW. This article puts the research of the "Belt and Road" construction under the framework of building a community with a shared future for humanity, and fully demonstrates the relationship between the two, which is conducive to making up the gaps in the field of research, and is also conducive to the improvement of the idea of building a community with a shared future for humanity and the "Belt and Road" construction research framework. At present, the integration of the knowledge related to this article is roughly as follows:

Firstly, the study of how to build a community with a shared future for humanity, Ming Hao believes that the construction of the “Belt and Road” can promote the people along the route to establish a sense of human destiny and build a community with a shared future for humanity [1, P.13]. From the steps of building a community with a shared future for humanity, Li Jingzhi believes that the community with a shared future for humanity is a grand vision, which can start from the construction of a community within a country, and then gradually expand to form a larger inter-regional community, and promote the formation of the community with a shared future for humanity in the process of in-depth exchanges and integration of countries, and in the process of the world's material level of continuous development to reach a higher level [2, P.27]. For the ideal goal of whether it can realize the community with a shared future for humanity, foreign scholars have a large difference in differences. The negative point of view believes that building a community with a shared future for humanity is full of idealism and does not have feasibility. With the traditional thinking concept, they believe that today's world can use limited resources, "win-win" are just the result of the parties who have to compromise. The complexity of reality will directly hinder the realization of good economic cooperation [3, P.226].

Secondly, the study of the "Belt and Road": Huo Jianguo, from a diplomatic point of view, believes that the implementation of the "Belt and Road" can make China's diplomatic relations with Central Asia, South Asia and other countries in the region to a new level, in order to consolidate the basis of cooperation between China and the countries along the line [4, P.7-10]. From the perspective of its economic objectives, Liu Weidong believes that the construction of the "Belt and Road" can promote a wider range of cooperation, enable the free flow of economic factors between countries, the rational allocation of various resources, and in particular, open up the international market, which will lead to the prosperity of the region as a whole [5, P.538-544]. Some foreign scholars believe that the "Belt and Road" continues the important spirit of the ancient Silk Road in terms of cultural inheritance, and compared with the "New Silk Road Program" proposed by the United States, it is more able to arouse people's emotional resonance, and will play a more significant role in the future [6, P.297]. According to political commentator Abduvali Soyibnazarov, Uzbekistan can take advantage of China's "Belt and Road" to bring local products to the markets of China and other countries, to attract investments in the main spheres of the national economy, and thus to complete the logistical opportunities [7]. There are also scholars who point out that some countries have a lukewarm attitude towards the construction of the "Belt and Road", such as some countries in Europe

that want to reap the economic benefits of it, but are also worried that joining it will involve various political risks, and say that they still need to continue to wait and see [8, P.33-42].

Thirdly, the relationship between the idea of building a community with a shared future for humanity and the construction of the “Belt and Road”: According to Li Yueming, the idea of building a community with a shared future for humanity provides theoretical guidance for promoting the construction of the “Belt and Road”, while the construction of the “Belt and Road” is the concrete implementation of its practical dimension [9, P.40-46]. Some foreign scholars believe that the construction of the “Belt and Road” involves a wide range of areas, which is consistent with the areas included in the community with a shared future for humanity, and is the best path to build a community with a shared future for humanity [10, P.3-22]. In terms of the relationship between the two, domestic and foreign academics have basically reached a consensus, but there are still imperfections in their arguments.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY. The article uses the methods of comparative studies, analysis, synthesis, extrapolation.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS. The idea of the community with a shared future for mankind is a new concept of human society raised in the complex issue of the world situation in the face of the background of the globalization. Shared safety community and green low-carbon ecological community. In 2013, the concept of the “Belt and Road” was officially proposed that as the deepening of the concept of building the community with a shared future for mankind, the “Belt and Road” provided an effective regional cooperation platform for the joint development of countries along the route.

In November 2012, China proposed for the first time “the community with a shared future for mankind”. It is rooted in the excellent traditional culture of the Chinese nation, which is characterized by the values of “peace is precious”, “harmony is different”, “thinking of righteousness in the face of profit”, and “law and morality”. The excellent traditional culture of the Chinese nation has inherited and developed the idea of “true community” in the core values of contemporary China, as well as the great achievements based on the concept of “community” nurtured by Western philosophical thought, providing a Chinese solution for the sustainable development of mankind in the context of globalization. It provides a Chinese proposal for the sustainable development of mankind in the context of globalization.

In March 2013, President Xi Jinping mentioned the community with a shared future for mankind during his visit to Russia and made a relevant elaboration, that is, human beings living on the same planet, in today’s increasingly interconnected world, the relationship is getting closer and closer, and countries with different systems, types and stages of development are interdependent and have intertwined interests, which has gradually formed a community with a shared future in which “you have me, and I have you”. In 2017, the concept of the community with a shared future for mankind has become the idea of building the community with a shared future for mankind under the promotion of Chinese officials. At this point, the core connotation of the idea is to “build lasting peace, universal security, common prosperity, openness, and clean and beautiful world.” It can be seen from the connotation that the community with a shared future for mankind contains various aspects of politics, economy, culture, ecology, and security, and is a comprehensive community.

Subsequently, the basic forms of “Asian community of shared future”, “China Africa community with a shared future”, “China ASEAN community with a shared future” were continuously formed. Today, the idea of building the community with a shared future for mankind is still enriching and perfect, and it will be further implemented and practiced in the present and future. It is an important idea to call on humans to act and put forward the common interests of the entire human beings.

The idea of the community with a shared future for mankind is based on the realities and conditions of the world, with strategies and initiatives planned, as well as realistic paths for cooperation with other countries. In September and October 2013, the year following of the community with a shared future for mankind was proposed, the cooperative initiatives of building the “Silk Road Economic Belt” and the “21st Century Maritime Silk Road” were successively proposed.

The two are collectively known as the “Belt and Road” initiative. The connotation of the “Belt and Road” can be summarized as “five links and three communities”, which is a unity of policy communication, facility connectivity, unimpeded trade, financial integration, and people-to-people bonds, and a community of shared interests, shared responsibilities, and shared decisions about the future. Through the five major aspects of policy formulation, infrastructure construction, foreign trade, financial support and public recognition, we will build a community of interests, responsibilities and a community with a shared future among the member countries of the “Belt and Road” initiative. Meeting the needs of China’s development “going out” while benefiting the people of countries along the route.

The “Belt and Road” concept aims to jointly build a community of a shared future featuring political mutual trust, economic win-win, and cultural tolerance through economic cooperation and friendly exchanges with countries along the route. The “Belt and Road” concept proposed by China has brought a good opportunity to China. At the same time, this opportunity has turned into an opportunity for the world. Through the “Belt and Road”, countries around the world have been able to complement each other’s strengths and achieve a win-win situation economically. The concept of the “Belt and Road” also serves as a bridge to promote cultural exchanges among the peoples of the world. Although the regions of the world are different and their cultures are different, what the “Belt and Road” brings about is not a clash of cultures, but rather exchanges and learning among civilizations.

The “Belt and Road”, which creatively inherits and carries forward the ancient Silk Road, a historical and civilizational achievement of humankind, and gives it a new spirit of the times and humanistic connotations, provides a practical platform for the countries along the route to participate in, build and benefit from the project, and for the building of the community with a shared future for mankind.

The “Belt and Road” runs through Eurasia, the East Economic Circle in the east, and the European economic circle in the west to the African continent. It is a desire to accelerate development in response to the requirements of the times. In terms of concepts, measures, goals, etc. The development agenda is highly consistent, and strives to build a community of interests, a community of responsibility, and a community with a shared future.

Build the “Belt and Road” initiative into a peaceful, prosperous, open, green, innovative and civilized road. It can be seen that the “Belt and Road” cooperation has many goals and significance, which is consistent with the core connotation of the idea of building a community with a shared future for mankind. The idea of building a community with a shared future for mankind and the construction of the “Belt and Road” are an organic combination of theory and practice. The idea of building a community with a shared future for mankind provides theoretical guidance and value pursuit for promoting the construction of the “Belt and Road”. The construction of the “Belt and Road” is a realistic path to the concept of building a community with a shared future for mankind, and its construction results everywhere demonstrate the idea of building a community with a shared future for mankind.

The idea of building a community with a shared future for mankind provides value guidance for promoting the construction of the “Belt and Road” initiative. The idea of building a community with a shared future for mankind involves five levels: politics, security, economy, culture, and ecology. Politically, it advocates mutual respect and equal consultation to build a world of lasting peace; in terms of security, it adheres to a new security concept of common, comprehensive, cooperative and sustainable to build a world of universal security; economically, it advocates working together in the same boat and building a common world and a prosperous world; culturally, it emphasizes respecting the diversity of world civilizations and building a world of tolerance and mutual learning; ecologically, it advocates environmental friendliness, green development, and building a clean and beautiful world. Although the “Belt and Road” construction is inclined to the economic level, through economic and trade exchanges, it is an important goal to achieve cooperation in politics, security, culture, and ecology. It is a road to peace, a road to prosperity, a road to openness, a road to green, the road to civilization has long been an important part of its construction. If the “Belt

and Road” construction is to truly share development opportunities and achieve win-win goals for all countries, it must adhere to the value concept of building a community with a shared future for mankind, and requires countries to adhere to the principle of mutual benefit when conducting cooperation and seek common economic development through interests, gradually reach a friendly consensus in the political field, maintain world peace, security and stability, protect the earth’s homeland on which mankind depends for survival, strengthen inter-regional cultural exchanges and reference, enhance understanding and recognition among people, thereby forming a prosperous community with a shared future for common development and common prosperity. It can be seen that the idea of building a community with a shared future for mankind can play a leading role in the construction of the “Belt and Road” and promote the construction of the “Belt and Road” in a better direction.

From January to June 2013, Chinese companies invested 80.17 billion yuan in non-financial direct investment in the “Belt and Road” partners, an increase of 23.3% year -on -year. However, January to March 2024, only three months, Chinese enterprises have built a national non-financial direct investment of 54.32 billion yuan in the “Belt and Road”, an increase of 12% year -on -year (USD 7.65 billion in US dollars, an increase of 8%).

In terms of foreign contracting projects, Chinese enterprises have established a national newly-signed contract of 284.96 billion yuan in the “Belt and Road”, an increase of 15% (the US dollar is 40.12 billion U.S. dollars, an increase of 10.9%), Increased by 7.9% (the US dollar was 25.99 billion U.S. dollars, an increase of 4%)

In the past 10 years, China has actively built the free trade zone with partners to inspire the release of cooperation potential. On the one hand, since the establishment of the “Belt and Road” initiative in 2013, it has been proposed that in the past 10 years, China has signed more than 200 cooperation documents for the “Belt and Road” with more than 150 countries and more than 30 international organizations; Investment scale creates 420,000 jobs for the joint construction of the country to help nearly 40 million people get rid of poverty. It is estimated that by 2030, the joint construction of the “Belt and Road” will cause 7.6 million people in relevant countries to get rid of extreme poverty and 32 million people to get rid of moderate poverty, which will increase global revenue by 0.7% to 2.9%. On the other hand, the “Belt and Road” project has greatly improved the quality of life of the local people. China and co -construction countries have carried out rich cooperation in public health and medical care to benefit the development results.

At the same time, Promote civilized exchanges and mutual learning. In the past 10 years, the construction of the “Belt and Road” has demonstrated to the world the openness and tolerance of the Chinese nation, such as being generous and virtuous, treating friends and neighbors well and treating all nations well, as well as promoting the excellent traditional Chinese culture. Gradually establish more than 10 cultural exchanges and educational cooperation brands such as “Luban Workshop”. By hosting exhibitions, film festivals and other activities, promoting Chinese civilization to the world, discovering the value of the times of joint construction of national culture, and promoting the common development of human civilization in the promotion of mutual appreciation of civilizations. As of 2022, China and 142 countries in the “Belt and Road” of China have signed an agreement or memorandum in the field of cultural tourism; Organizational participation in individual countries has cultivated more than 119,000 scientific and technological talents.

Conclusion

Today’s world is experiencing a new round of great development and change, and at the same time, it is also facing many challenges, such as climate change, resource shortages, and the widening gap between the rich and the poor, etc, and the international system and order are undergoing deep adjustments, and the development of human civilization is facing new opportunities and new challenges. From the perspective of common destiny and overall interests of mankind, building a community with a shared future for humanity was put forward in 2012, and the “Belt and Road” construction, as an innovative new form of cooperation and new practice, is an important practical platform to promote the building of a community with a shared future for humanity. In the past 10 years, the “Belt and Road” initiative has been transformed from an initiative into a practice, and has

made real and substantial achievements, becoming an effective path to promote the construction of a community with a shared future for humanity.

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ЖИЛД 5, СОН 1

ЖУРНАЛ РЕНЕССАНСА ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 1

JOURNAL OF CENTRAL ASIAN RENAISSANCE

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 1

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